

A Study of Work Stress Experienced by its Employees Working in Multinational Corporations in Telangana, India

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Abstract

The past decade has witnessed a global and national surge in concerns surrounding work stress and its detrimental effect on organizational well-being. This trend is unsurprising considering the centrality of work in modern society, the increasing amount of time people dedicate to their jobs, and the ongoing transformations that are fundamentally altering the nature of work itself. Research suggests a clear link between repetitive tasks and dehumanizing work environments, such as those found on traditional assembly lines, and a decline in physical health. Stress can also stem from feelings of isolation or conflict within the workplace. This conflict can arise from disagreements with colleagues, or even more serious issues like harassment or discrimination. To gain a deeper understanding of this phenomenon, a pilot study was conducted within multinational IT companies located in Telangana, India. The study employed a simple random sampling technique to gather data from a sample size of 100 IT employees. A structured questionnaire was utilized to collect data from the sample population. The results revealed a key demographic trend: the majority of the surveyed employees belonged to the 20-25 year old age group. Furthermore, the study indicated that roughly two-thirds of these IT professionals fell within the monthly income bracket of Rs 10,000 to Rs 15,000. Interestingly, the data also showed that the majority of the surveyed employees were single. In terms of experience, one-third of the IT professionals had been working in the industry for 1-2 years. The study also aimed to identify the key factors contributing to work stress among these IT employees. The findings highlighted several prominent stressors, including Inadequate Salary , Overtime, Time Pressure , Workload , Insufficient Holidays , Night Shifts.

Keywords: MNC Companies, Stress, MNC employees, Telangana, Regression, Frequency and Percentage Analysis, ANOVA.

INTRODUCTION

Work Stress affects people of all ages and isn't just a human problem. Research by Bruce McEwen (2002; McEwen & Wingfield, 2010) shows that work stress acts as a two-way street, triggering a response and being caused by external pressures. The good news is, humans have developed a toolbox of coping mechanisms – activities we can use to manage or even overcome stress.

Hans Selye, a pioneer in stress research, initially defined work stress as a "nonspecific neuroendocrine response" within the body (Selye, 1936, 1956, 1971, 1974, 1976). Learning to manage this response effectively can be challenging. However, scientific research has yielded numerous methods for stress control.

Interestingly, Work stress can have a positive influence. Eustress, a form of positive Work stress, can stimulate the body's systems to function at optimal levels. This can even lead to personal growth for some individuals, as Judith Orloff (2009) suggests, particularly after periods of crisis or trauma. The key lies in how individuals react to Work stress. Mathews, Zeidner, and Roberts (2006) emphasize the importance of emotional intelligence in managing stress. They highlight the ability to read and respond sensitively to social situations and effectively manage emotions as crucial factors in stress management. Through emotional intelligence, individuals can not only deal with internal stress but also prevent conflict with others.

The modern workplace is a significant source of Work stress, as Kottler and David (2011) point out. Rapid changes in the nature of work, coupled with evolving legal definitions, have led to a dramatic increase in claims associated with chronic work-related stress. Previously, stress claims were primarily linked to traumatic events like violence or accidents. However, Sivasubramaniam and Rajandran (2017) highlight a recent shift, where chronic Work stress has become the leading cause of such claims. The financial and human costs associated with chronic work stress are vast, though often challenging to quantify due to factors like misleading statistics, unreported cases, employee turnover, and inconsistent record-keeping.

Research has established a clear link between specific job conditions and mental and physical health. Poor working conditions, characterized by pressure to work quickly, physical exertion, or inconvenient work hours, have been directly linked to negative mental health

outcomes. Similarly, repetitive tasks and dehumanizing environments, like assembly lines, have been shown to adversely affect physical health.

Social interactions within the workplace can also be a source of stress. Isolation, rejection by colleagues, perceived discrimination, and even public contact involving hostility or prejudice can all contribute to stress levels.

Considering this complex interplay between stress and work, this study aims to identify the factors contributing to stress among women employees working from home in IT MNCs located in Telangana, India. By investigating the influence of these stress indicators on overall work stress levels, the study hopes to provide valuable insights for developing effective stress management strategies within this specific demographic.

1.1. Scope of Study

Since work stress affects everyone differently, understanding individual reactions is key to managing stress for ourselves and others. Reducing stress is crucial for well-being. This study examines how role stress impacts IT employees, considering both role and work environment factors. By analyzing these factors, we can diagnose current work systems and identify areas for improvement to promote employee growth, development, and engagement.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sangeeta and Nidhi(2013) founded on Interrelationships between work stress due to Inadequate Salary and Rewards in Indian army officers. The research carried out among Indian army officer. The sampling size was 50. The researcher used 5point likert Scale Questionnaire for primary data collection and used T-Test and Correlation. The researcher found there is a relationship between the dimensions of marital discord, inadequate salary and rewards were connected the level of stress rises because of inadequate Salary and rewards, marital discord also increases. Indian army personnel are dissatisfied with their salary and promotion policies.

Darshani (2014) investigated on Personality Types and Locus of control as moderators of stress Conflict management. The researcher reveals these strategies can be either problem focused on emotional focused Taking decisions are sudden and unexpected. highlighting the importance of both problem-focused and emotion-focused approaches..

Sanjeev and Bhukar(2013) Compared stress level and coping strategies of college students. The research carried out among Professional students. The sampling size was 60. The researcher used two-way ANOVA. The researcher revealed the women had higher level of work stress than men as the women have more challenges to follow Indian Orthodox customs, prevailing in the society. Stress affects the brain with its many nerve connections; the rest of the body feels the impact as well.

Abdul.et.al (2014) Examined research on Job stress and Job Satisfaction among healthcare professionals. The research carried out among healthcare professionals. The Sampling size was 620 and used Simple Random Sampling Technique, Linear regression analysis, Pearson Correlation test. The researcher reveals the current workplace environment could increase the risk of stress among health care professionals. However the satisfaction rate was high and not negatively associated with low work stress levels.

Sameera, Shaik and Firoz (2016) had done a research on stress management among the BPO employees in Chennai city. The research was carried among Nationalized BPO employees in Chennai. The sampling size was 100.The researchers used Percentage analysis and MS Excel. The researchers found a large number of the employees fear with the fact that lack quality in their work puts stress on them. It is found that maximum number of employees in BPO remains in work stress. More than half of the employees feel that they are overloaded with work. Maximum employees feel tensed due to their non-achievement of targets in the work. Half of the employees accepted that there is fight among the employees. It is a concern for top management. Feel that plans used by BPO Firms to manage stress of employees are effective. Majority of the MNC employees try to find solution to relieve them from work stress. Average of the employees practice YOGA or other ways to relieve them from stress, majority of the employees balance in their social life. Direction and counseling, Quality awareness Psychological funding should be provided to the employees.

3. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Work stress has become a pervasive issue for employees across all industries, with the work-life balance becoming increasingly difficult to maintain. As a result, work stress management techniques are gaining traction as employees seek ways to cope with pressure. These strategies empower individuals to improve their response to stress while enabling

organizations to reduce workplace stressors. This study specifically focuses on investigating work stress (inadequate salary , Overtime , Time Pressure, Work Load , insufficient holiday , Night Shift) among IT employees in Telangana.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Objective of the Study

- I. To examine the factors contributing work stress among IT employees.

4.2. Hypotheses of the Study

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between inadequate salary and IT Employees

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Overtime and IT Employees

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Time Pressure and IT Employees

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Work Load and IT Employees

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between insufficient holiday and IT Employees

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Night Shift and IT Employees

4.3. Area of the Study

This study focuses specifically on the IT sector within Telangana, India. While the IT sector itself was chosen deliberately due to its distinct service nature, the IT MNC companies and the IT employees participating in the study were selected randomly. This two-stage sampling approach employed purposive sampling for the sector and study area, followed by simple random sampling to select companies and IT employees. Data collection involved a pilot study utilizing a structured interview schedule administered through direct interviews with the participants. The study gathered information from 100 IT employees working in IT MNC companies in Telangana during the period of 2020-2021.

4.4. Sources of Data

Primary Data: Information was gathered directly from IT employees working in IT MNCs located in Telangana. This involved a pilot study followed by structured interviews.

Secondary Data: The study also reviewed existing research on the topic, including academic sources like journals, research papers, reports, conference proceedings, and relevant websites.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

5.1. Data Analysis

The data analysis has been done using IBM SPSS 23 (Statistical Package For Social Science)

5.2. Statistical Techniques

Descriptive Statistics: In order to identify the various factors which contribute towards increasing the work stress level of IT Employees in MNC Companies

Multiple Regressions: In order to study the effect of factors affecting IT Employees and its impact on work stress level in IT Employees. The functional form of multiple linear regression models is given below.

The Likert five point scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree) was used to measure the work stress dimensions and work stress indicators.

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Social background of IT Employees

Social background of IT employees in MNC Companies is collected for the analysis purpose and details are listed in table 1. The result shows that majority of the IT employees(64 %) are belongs male and female (36 %).The majority of the IT employees 81 % are belongs to the age group of 20-25and 19 % are belongs to 25 -30.The majority (81%) of the IT employees have completed their UG followed by PG of 16 % and Diploma 3%.The 81 % of IT employees are having the experience of below 5 years and 5-10 years are 19 %.The majority(92 %) IT employees are single and 8 % are married .The majority (58 %) ITemployees are 10000-15000, 5000-10000 are 20 % and 15000 to 20000 are (22 %)

Table 1 Social background of IT Employees in MNC Companies

Age	Frequency (Percentage)	Gender		Material Status	
20-25	81 (81%)	Male	64 (64 %)	Single	92 (92%)
25-30	19 (19%)	Female	36 (36 %)	Married	8 (8%)
Experience		Education		Salary	
Below5 years	81 (81%)	UG	81 (81%)	5000-10000	20 (20%)
5-10 years	19 (19%)	PG	16 (16%)	10000-15000	58 (58%)
		Diploma	3 (3%)	15000-20000	22 (22%)

Source: Primary Data

6.2 Factors Influences Stress level/ IT Employees in MNC Companies

Table 2 shows frequency and Percentage value of dependent variable namely Induces High Stress level and the independent variables such as Inadequate Salary, Over Time, Time Pressure, Work Load, Insufficient holidays, Night Shift.

Table 2

Factors Influences Stress level/IT	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neither Agree nor disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Inadequate Salary	10 (10 %)	63 (63 %)	15 (15 %)	8 (8 %)	4 (4 %)
Over Time	12 (10 %)	72 (10 %)	8 (8 %)	4 (4 %)	4 (4 %)
Time Pressure	32 (32 %)	48 (48 %)	10 (10 %)	7 (7 %)	3 (3 %)
Work Load	28 (28 %)	40 (40 %)	12 (12 %)	8 (8 %)	2 (2 %)
Insufficient holidays	35 (35 %)	59 (59 %)	5 (5 %)	1 (1 %)	0 (0 %)
Night Shift	32 (32 %)	47 (47 %)	11 (11 %)	6 (6 %)	4 (4 %)

Source: Primary Data

The figures in the parentheses are percentage total: primary and computed data

The table No 2 shows that 63 % of the respondents agreed and 10 % are strongly agreed that inadequate salary has induces high stress level on IT employees. The 72% of the respondents agreed and 12 % are strongly agreed that Over Time has induces high work stress level on IT employees.48% of the respondents agreed and 32% are strongly agreed that Time Pressure has induces high work stress level on IT employees. The 40% of the respondents agreed and 28% are strongly agreed that Work Load has induces high work stress level on IT employees.59% of the respondents agreed and 35% are strongly agreed that insufficient holidays has induces high work stress level on IT employees.47% of the respondents agreed and 32% are strongly agreed that Night Shift has induces high work stress level on IT employees.

6.3 Multiple Regression Analysis

In order to identify the influences of stress level impact (dependent variable) on customer service Representative of IT MNC Companies the multiple regression analysis by linear regression carried out and results presented in table 3

Table 3: Influences of factors on stress level of IT Employees-Multiple Regression

Stress Factors	Standardized Coefficient (Beta)	t-value	Sig.
Stress level in IT Employees			
Stress level increase due to Inadequate Salary	.513	3005	.003
Stress level increase due to Over Time	.905	7.101	.000
Stress level increase due to Time Pressure	.066	1.618	.107
Stress level increase due to Work Load	.527	4.629	.000
Stress level increase due to Insufficient holidays	.899	4.773	.000
Stress level increase due to Night Shift	.856	8.556	.000
Dependent Variables stress level in IT Employees **Indicates significant at 1% level *Indicates significant at 5% level			

Source: Primary Data

6.4. Results of Multi regression and Hypothesis

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between inadequate salary and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=0.513, $t=3.005$ and $p=0.003$ which is less than 0.05, indicates that there is strong relationship between the inadequate salary and IT employee. The null hypotheses was rejected and alternative hypotheses was accepted.

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Over Time and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=.905, $t=7.101$ and $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, indicates that there is strong relationship between the Over Time and IT employee. The null hypothesis was rejected and an alternative hypothesis was accepted.

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Time Pressure and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=.066, $t=1.618$ and $p=0.107$ which is more than 0.05, indicates that there is no significant relationship between the Time Pressure and IT employee. As such null hypotheses was accepted and alternative hypotheses was rejected

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Workload and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=0.527, $t=4.629$ and $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, indicates that there is strong relationship between the Work Load and IT employee. The null hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypotheses was accepted.

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between insufficient holidays and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=0.899, $t=4.773$ and $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, indicates that there is strong relationship between the insufficient holidays and IT employee. The null hypotheses was rejected and alternative hypotheses was accepted.

H₀ – There is no significant relationship between Night Shift and IT Employee, The result shows that B value=0.856, $t=8.556$ and $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.05, indicates that there is strong relationship between the Night Shift and IT employee. The null hypothesis was rejected and alternative hypotheses was accepted.

Linear regression analysis was done on the independent factors that induce stress level on the IT employees. The result shows that co efficient of multiple dimensions $R^2=0.653$ and adjusted $R^2=0.653$ indicating that the regression model is good fit. It inferred that about 65.3% of the variation in dependent variable (stress level) explained by independent variable of stress

level factors. The stress level increase due to inadequate Salary, over time, Time Pressure, Work Load Insufficient holidays, night shift are statistically significant 1% level and these factors have predicted the stress level of IT Employees.

The ANOVA test was carried out to examine the stress level of IT Employees due to Night Shift, the F-value of 62.268 ($p=0.000$) indicates that the regression model is a good fit between the stress level of IT Employees and its independent variables. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0), and accepted the alternative hypothesis. Except for the factor "Time Pressure" did not affect the stress level of IT employee.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the impact of various work stress factors on IT employees. It examined how factors like inadequate salary, overtime, time pressure, workload, insufficient holidays, and night shifts influence employee well-being. Interestingly, the research found that time pressure, when managed effectively, did not necessarily lead to negative consequences for IT employees. However, the remaining factors – inadequate salary, overtime, workload, insufficient holidays, and night shifts – were all confirmed to be significant contributors to work stress in this population.

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